

README

Title: Survey Dataset on Students' Personal Financial Management Education Assessment, Portfolio Risk and Future investment prospects, 2025.

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Description: The dataset contains information on students' personal financial management education assessment, level of risk acceptance, financial literacy and investment possibilities.

Data collection method: Cross-sectional survey with the use of structured questionnaire.

Sample information: N= 368 undergraduate and post graduate students.

File List:

- CSV version
- Codebook
- Readme

Anonymization statement: all data have been anonymized; no personal identifiable information has been included.

Usage notes: the data can safely be used for teaching, research and statistical analysis in the education sector.

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